

Left Ventricular Stroke Work and Ejection Fraction in Dilated Cardiomyopathy

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Abstract

In dilated cardiomyopathy, the left ventricular ejection fraction (EF) and the left ventricular stroke work per beat (SW) are reduced. In this study, the SW was calculated for several reduced levels of EF. Reductions of the EF were closely correlated ($r=0.98$) with reductions in the SW in a linear relationship. However, for each level of EF, there was a considerable variability in the SW, more in mild degrees of LV dysfunction, than in severe LV dysfunction.

Keywords: Stroke work ejection fraction.

Introduction

Stroke work is the quantity of mechanical energy expended by the LV to expel the stroke volume with each beat. It has been well known that in dilated cardiomyopathy, the SW is reduced, and continues to fall as the EF progressively declines (1). However, the relationship has not been clearly studied. In this study, the correlation between the SW and EF is examined, and an equation is derived to help predict the SW for a given EF.

Methods and Results

Hemodynamic data was obtained from several sources (2-8), although no actual patient data was used in this study.

Stroke Volume (SV) is the quantity of blood ejected by the LV with each beat. This is about 70 ml for an average size male. Stroke work is defined as: $SW=P \times V$ where V is the Stroke Volume, and P is the mean arterial pressure (MAP), defined as $MAP=Diastolic\ pressure + 1/3(Systolic\ pressure-diastolic\ pressure)$, therefore: $SW=SV \times MAP$.

Data for the range of SV and range of MAP were collected for Ejection Fractions of 15%, 25%, 35%, 45%, and 55% (normal EF). SW values were calculated and averaged for each EF grouping. See Table 1.

A graph (Figure 1) was made of the average SW (y axis) and the EF (x axis) for each group. This showed a correlation coefficient of $r=0.98$. The regression equation for this data was found to be $y= -0.074 + 1.95x$. For each EF group, some variability in the SW was found in each group, more in the 45% EF group and less in the 15% EF group.

Table 1.

EF (%)	15	25	35	45	55
SV (ml) range	20-30	30-50	50-70	60-100	70-100
MAP (mmHg) range	50-70	60-80	60-90	70-90	70-100
SW (joules per beat) range	0.20-0.28	0.20-0.53	0.40-0.84	0.56-1.2	0.65-1.3
SW (joules per beat) average	0.24	0.37	0.60	0.86	0.97

Figure 1

Discussion

This study is consistent with the concept that in dilated cardiomyopathy, the stroke work declines as the left ventricular EF declines, and that this is basically a linear relationship. The derived regression equation enables one to approximate the SW for any given EF. Interestingly, in mild cardiomyopathy (45% EF) there is a wide overlap of the SW with that seen with a normal EF. This suggests that with only mild impairment the heart is able to make compensatory adjustments to maintain a normal stroke volume. However, in the more severely impaired groups (25% and especially 15% EF), the range of the SW is much less, suggesting that the heart is so impaired that it cannot maintain anything close to a normal stroke volume, and this situation is likely to be permanent. Also, this gives further credence to the idea that those in the intermediate range (35% EF) should be treated as aggressively as possible to prevent the EF and the SW from declining any further.

Conclusions

The left ventricular SW can be reasonably approximated from the EF, as they are closely correlated in a linear relationship. This may have applications for treatment and prognosis of various cardiomyopathy patients.

References

1. Zipes D, Libby P, et al. 2021. Braunwald's Heart Disease: a Textbook of Cardiovascular Medicine, 12th edition, 889-1132. New York: Elsevier. ISBN-10 0323722199.
2. Mann D, Felker M. Mechanisms and models in heart failure. *Circ Res* 2021;128(10):158-162. Doi.org/10.1161/circresaha.121.318158.
3. Hsu S, Fary J. Hemodynamics for the heart failure clinician. *J Card Fail* 2021;28(1):133-148. Doi:10.1016/j.cardfail.2021.07.012.
4. DeMers D, Wachs D. Physiology. *Nat Lib Med* 2023, April 10, Stat Pearls [Internet]. Treasure Island, Fla: Stat Pearls Publishing.
5. Stouffer G. 2017. Cardiovascular dynamics for the clinician, 2nd edition, Hoboken: Wiley Blackwell.
6. Bruss Z, Raja A. Physiology, Stroke Volume. *Nat Lib Med* 2022.